

THETIDA

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

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Abstract

The THETIDA project approaches safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change (CC) and natural hazards in a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to Cultural Heritage(CH) sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas. The THETIDA project achieves this goal through the development of a preventive conservation strategy that includes monitoring, risk preparedness and management, for underwater and coastal CH (U&C-CH) sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote adaptation, reconstruction and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to CC and to wield policy tools for economic resilience. In this project, an interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts and practitioners will develop, test and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments and through participatory processes (Citizens' Science and Living Labs). The project implementation actions will link the social innovations with cutting-edge technologies (ICT and IoT harmonised tools).

Consortium

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Disclaimer of warranties

This document is part of the deliverables from the THETIDA project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101095253.

This project has partially used a standard methodology already developed in the CARDIMED project (Grant Agreement number: 101112731), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the conditions of the Grant Agreement for THETIDA project (Grant Agreement number: 101095253).

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

Executive Summary

Deliverable 7.1 provides an overview of personal data protection and ethical aspects within the THETIDA project. The document focuses on ethical processes in project activities, gender and non-discrimination aspects, identification and recruitment of participants and procedures to be followed to obtain informed consent from participants. Finally, the document provides templates for informed consent forms and information sheets to be used throughout the activities of the project.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CC	Climate Change
CH	Cultural Heritage
D7.1	Deliverable number 1 belonging to WP 7
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
DOI	Data Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EIM	Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights Manager
ELC	Ethics and Legal Committee
ES	ETSI Standard
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Green House Gas
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
SSH	Secure Shell protocol
SSL	Secure Socket Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
U&C	Underwater & Coastal
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Coordinator

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

THETIDA is expected to collect data that will be derived from the participation of diverse stakeholders and end users across various countries through their participation in project activities which will involve citizen science activities, workshops, interviews, surveys, and questionnaires.

Each member of THETIDA leading or participating in tasks that involve human participants will ensure the respect for people and for human dignity, fair distribution of the benefits and burden of research, and the protection of the values, rights and interests of the research participants.

The main purpose of D7.1 is to provide an insight about the procedures to be followed about the protection of personal data collected from project activities. The main aims of the document are to:

- Clarify the processing procedures of personal data that will be collected for the purposes of the THETIDA project.
- Provide the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented to protect the rights and freedoms of data subjects and participants.
- Provide security measures to prevent unauthorized access to personal data or the equipment used for processing.
- Describe the internal Ethics review procedure.

1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable is labelled public and intended for a readership comprising the members of THETIDA consortium, the European Commission services as well as the wider public. This deliverable includes the templates that will assist and guide the work of THETIDA partners, satisfying the highest ethical standards.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1:** presents the Introduction of the deliverable.
- **Section 2:** provides a summary of ethical aspects and General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR).
- **Section 3:** outlines the THETIDA ethical framework to manage ethical aspects and provides the processes to be followed for participation of stakeholders/end users and provides guidelines for THETIDA partners when engaging with external participants.
- **Section 4:** presents the main conclusions of the deliverable.

- **Annexes:** provide the ethics and legal review template, list of deliverables that may contain legal and ethical issues and templates to be used for THETIDA activities with external stakeholders.

2. Ethics summary report

From submission of proposal phase to the implementation of Grant Agreement (GA), THETIDA project has followed the Ethics Appraisal Process [1]. Based on the Ethics Summary Report that was delivered during the GA preparation, THETIDA has Ethics clearance and is an Ethics ready project, while an Ethics Review was deemed as necessary during the implementation phase of the project. The General requirement applicable to all grants also apply to THETIDA project with involved beneficiaries to ensure that all ethics issues related to activities in the grant are addressed in compliance with ethical principles, the applicable international and national laws, and the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement.

2.1 Do No Significant Harm principle

THETIDA will ensure that it is fully compliant with the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) Principle since its activities as well as the expected life cycle impact of the innovations, substantially contribute in a positive way and/or do not significantly harm any of the six environmental objectives set out in Art. 9 and 17 of the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation (EU) 2020/852 [2]. THETIDA will apply a life-cycle oriented approach to ensure that proposed solutions are sustainable through the following steps: 1) Identification of actual and potential adverse impacts during the life cycle of the project activities; 2) Prevention or mitigation of adverse impacts; and 3) Accounting for how adverse impacts are addressed by tracking performance and communicating results. Lifecycle GHG emissions and net emissions will be calculated using Recommendation 2013/179/EU or, alternatively, using ETSI ES 203 199, ISO 14067:2018 or ISO 14064-2:2019.

2.2 General Data Protection Regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [3] provides a common legal framework for all EU Member states and sets guidelines for the collection and processing of personal information of individuals within the European Union (Regulation 2016/679 EU). It applies to all companies processing the personal data of data subjects residing in the Union, regardless of the company's location. The GDPR makes its applicability very clear – it applies to the processing of personal data by controllers and processors in the EU, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the EU or not. The GDPR also applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects not established in the EU by a controller or processor in the EU, where the activities relate to: offering goods or services to EU citizens (irrespective of whether

payment is required) and the monitoring of behaviour that takes place within the EU. Non-EU businesses processing the data of EU citizens also have to appoint a representative in the EU. The GDPR also has an impact on research activities. International research consortium must implement a data processing compliant with the GDPR (art. 6, 7, 8, 9, 13, 14 of the GDPR), releasing a proper information sheet and consent form.

2.2.1 Personal data

Personal data is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual [4]. Examples of personal data include:

- a name and surname;
- a home address;
- an email address such as name.surname@company.com;
- an identification card number;
- location data (for example the location data function on a mobile phone);
- an Internet Protocol (IP) address;

Examples of what is NOT considered personal data:

- a company registration number;
- an email address such as info@company.com;
- anonymised data.

The following sensitive personal data [5] will not be processed during THETIDA project:

- personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs;
- trade-union membership;
- genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being;
- health-related data;
- data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation.

3. THETIDA ethical framework

3.1 Management of ethical aspects

Potential matters requiring legal expertise or related to privacy protection, ethics/gender considerations will be handled by the THETIDA Ethics and IPR Manager (EIM), as indicated in D7.3 [6]. The THETIDA EIM, Evangelia Portouli (ICCS), is responsible for:

- Monitoring the legal, ethical and security activities of the project (ensuring that all evaluations follow ethical and legal procedures as relevant to National and European regulations).
- Keeping record of all potential legal, privacy and ethical issues as the THETIDA services and tools are evaluated and demonstrated in the pilots; all

participatory activities of the project with human participants are going to be monitored that they abide by the EU GDPR rules following the Ethical Appraisal Procedure abided by the Horizon Europe grant scheme; the same will apply for generated or used data from the pilots ensuring that sensitive data are anonymised and stored according to the EU regulations.

- Ensuring that Social Science Humanities (SSH) is embedded in the project as an enabler of Responsible Research Innovation (RRI).
- Monitoring any gender aspects which arise and overseeing the promotion of gender equality.

To support the aforementioned activities an Ethics & Legal Committee (ELC) has been formed to provide supervision on relevant aspects and critical input when and if there is deviation from common standards, directives and best practices. The EIM with the support of ELC will ensure the proper adoption of the legal, ethical and security framework of the THETIDA solutions and is keeping a record of all potential ethical issues that arise as the prototypes are developed and evaluated, and all ethical issues that arise through discussion with the stakeholders and Living Labs (LL) activities. The ELC is chaired by the EIM (ICCS) and includes one member from partners participating in T7.3 (i.e. UNIPD, NTUA, UAlg, CMMI, CCVALg, EURISY). An ethics and legal review decision form (presented in Annex I) has also been compiled and is filled by the EIM and/or ELC for deliverables (presented in Annex II) that may contain legal, ethical or security issues.

3.2 Vulnerable groups

As part of THETIDA activities, the project will also focus on investigating vulnerable user groups and aspects related with mobility needs, requirements, concerns, and expectations, while children and minors are not foreseen to be included in THETIDA activities. In conducting research with vulnerable populations such as elderly persons and persons with disabilities, extra attention will be taken to protect their rights and ensure that their compliance is freely given. In this context, THETIDA will ensure a full understanding by all participants of the information given when inviting them to participate in a study protocol providing relevant information sheets and consent forms in an accessible way, written and/or online depending on each occasion. Particular focus will be paid to informing vulnerable groups about their ability to give or withdraw consent; ensuring in parallel that the study subjects are not selected or rejected for the wrong reasons and that there are no secondary or hidden interests when performing the research.

3.3 Gender aspects and non-discrimination

THETIDA promotes equal opportunities between men and women and aims, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the tasks, including at a supervisory and managerial level. Principles of equal treatment of men

and women are followed across all activities in the project. All participants will be treated equally irrespective of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation. In THETIDA project there is a strong presence of women as Work Package leaders and participating partners. Further to this, we will also promote gender balance among the various stakeholders that will be engaged as part of the project, including in the Living Lab workshops.

THETIDA activities are expected to contribute to exposing and understanding gender differentiated environmental practices. This aspect will be considered during the employment of LLs in WP3, in which the gender dimension will be intersected with other social dimensions, such as ecological, age and other inequalities with regard to i) technologies, digitalisation, new business and governance models, and social and environmental innovation; ii) socially disadvantaged regions; iii) representation and voice in the process of capturing the end-users needs; and iv) interactive and integrated approaches to fair and just pathways will be investigated and assessed. The main outcome of the gender analysis and the intersectional factors, such as ethnicity and socioeconomic status, would be to ensure environmentally friendly measures that support social equality and avoid social harms. Furthermore, the project will also focus on embedding positive gender norms in policy recommendations by putting into practice participatory research that will enable new policies to be conceptualised from citizen perspectives through a gender-sensitive framework. This method will result in policy recommendations that add new insights into the relevant policies, involving identification of the influence of gender roles and relations on the use, management and respond to the climate transition.

3.4 Ethics processes for participation of stakeholders/end-users

This section focuses on the processes that will be followed for participation of stakeholders and end users at project activities. THETIDA will involve various participants conducting activities in 7 pilot demonstrations across the EU. Participants in THETIDA events will be identified or recruited by consortium partners. These may include internal staff of THETIDA partners and, external individuals whose contact details are accessible to the consortium partners. Participants may also be found through third-party organizations with whom the consortium has affiliations, or through snowballing technique. Additional stakeholders and the general public will be further engaged during the activities of various WPs (e.g. WP1 and WP3 in which citizen science workshops/focus groups will be conducted with internal and external stakeholders, WP2 and WP5 which crowdsourcing activities will be implemented, WP6 in which joint events with other projects will take place).

Participation in THETIDA activities will be voluntary and informed, while involvement will be restricted to adult participants who possess the capability to provide explicit,

written, freely-given, specific, and informed consent before participating in any THETIDA event. Before participation, individuals will receive written or verbal information about THETIDA project objectives and then they are expected to reaffirm their consent to participate. Formal written invitations, including detailed information on THETIDA goals for the specific activity and a tailored Informed Consent form (Annex VI), to external participants are expected to be sent at least three weeks prior to scheduled THETIDA activities. The Informed Consent forms need to be read, understood, and signed prior to the scheduled project activity. Throughout the process, participants need to have constant access to THETIDA partners for guidance and support. The consortium partner representative's contact information is also provided for on-demand advice, in case that is required by participants.

3.4.1 Informed consent procedures

The following guidelines will be followed to ensure compliance with ethical, privacy, and security principles with regards to the data collected from participants during THETIDA activities.

- Participants will have the right to decline participation in THETIDA activities.
- In the case of activities taking place in local communities, local and/or national authorities will be informed about them, their purpose, the type of data collected and consent from local authorities will be sought where appropriate.
- Prior to providing their consent, participants will be informed about the project's purpose, research goals, data usage, storage, deletion procedures, and any potential effects of participation.
- For project demonstrations, THETIDA partners will receive specific guidance to ensure informing participants in an accurate way about the event's purpose, provide details on participation procedures, and clarify to participants that it is an example rather than a real-life situation.
- Participants must give voluntary informed consent to participate in the activity, while they will be informed of their right to withdraw from project activities and there will be no discrimination against them.

Informed consent for all THETIDA activities will be obtained by having participants to read a project information sheet (Annex III), discuss potential risks arising from the participation in the activity and sign a written consent form. In cases where signing the consent form is impractical, such as during an ad-hoc interview on a demo site tour, consent may be documented through audio or video recording. When feasible, consent from an organizational representative will be sought. Participants may also request to be removed from research records if practicable.

For the purposes of the procedures described in this section the following templates have been developed and provided as Annexes:

- THETIDA information sheet (see Annex III);

- THETIDA letter of request to participate in a[workshop/interview/intervention] template (see Annex IV);
- Informed consent form (see Annex V);
- Consent for publishing photos and videos (see Annex VI).

3.4.2 Processing of personal data

Data obtained from participants during THETIDA activities will not include sensitive personal information and will be processed based on existing legislation and regulations [6]. Consortium partners are also expected to seek approval from local ethics committees before collecting participant data.

3.4.3 Right to withdraw

Participants will be informed of their right to withdraw from THETIDA activities, without specifying a reason, and are also provided with a list of potential risks and benefits that derive from their participation at the activity. They should also be notified and provide their consent in case of audio recording, electronic note-taking while they can instruct the interviewer to stop, start, or delete any part of the recorded material. This right will be communicated during the informed consent process, while in case of a withdraw this can be communicated orally.

3.4.4 Privacy of voluntary interviewed participants

During THETIDA project, a diverse set of participatory tools will be employed, i.e. focus groups, co-mapping, excursions, interviews. Beneficiaries responsible for these activities will ensure that participants receive a detailed information sheet prior to the activity. The information sheet will cover aspects such as the following: project background and objectives, reasons for participation, questions to be asked, collected information, data usage, access details, potential risks, researcher contacts, participant rights (voluntariness, withdrawal, data erase aspects), data procedures (including sensitive information, if relevant) to be followed, data storage, basic principles, interview location, and recording methods. The information sheet is presented in a clear and understandable language and translated if that is required.

After participants have understood the information sheet, they will be asked to provide voluntary informed consent, which is essential and is required both prior to and throughout their involvement in the activities of THETIDA. They will also have the opportunity to pose questions and receive clear answers before deciding to participate. Each participant will be provided a consent form and information sheet prior to the event (see also Annex I and III). The participant and the lead beneficiary will retain a copy of the signed consent and Information Sheet. In case of a verbal consent, the process will be witnessed, recorded, and dated. The lead beneficiary will provide the completed consent sheet to the Project Coordinator (PC) either via email or in person and the consent sheet will be securely saved in a dedicated area on the THETIDA SharePoint platform which will be accessed only by the relevant WP leader, EIM and PC.

3.4.5 Guidelines for THETIDA partners when engaging external participants

Any partner that is engaging external stakeholders as participants for any activity, should follow the procedure below.

Each external participant should receive the *THETIDA information sheet (Annex III)*.

- *The THETIDA information sheet does not have to be signed.*
- *The THETIDA partner that will be engaging the external participants, should replace greyed-out sections of the THETIDA information sheet with the information of the partner.*

In addition, depending on the activity the external participant will be engaged in, each participant should receive either:

- *The THETIDA letter of request to participate in a [workshop/interview/intervention] template (Annex IV);*
- *The THETIDA informed consent form (Annex V);*
- *Consent for publishing photos and videos (Annex VI).*
- *The relevant document must be signed by the external participant.*

All templates are provided in English in the Annexes and should be translated by the consortium partners whenever necessary and will be available in the THETIDA SharePoint platform.

Therefore, when engaging external participants required documents should be printed (by organising partner) and consent form should be signed (by the external participants). When organizing local / national events, external participants may not understand the English language. In those cases, the organizing THETIDA partner must translate the documents.

3.5 THETIDA project measures

3.5.1 Administrative safeguards

Administrative safeguards refer to a set of policies, procedures, and practices employed to ensure the overall security of systems. For THETIDA administrative safeguards will consist of the following measures:

- ICCS will serve as the project Data Controller who is responsible to maintain and handle personal data in accordance with national / local protection laws.
- THETIDA partners contributing to data are considered Data Contributors responsible for providing personal data in accordance with applicable national / local protection laws. Data Contributors are responsible for storing linkage information required for the re-identification of a separate database utilising server-side encryption and tightly controlled access. Data Contributors will

also maintain the property of the data provided and that data will be returned and will not be further used by the Data Controller and/or Data Processors after the end of the project.

- THETIDA partners using the data for project purposes are Data Processors who will have access to the data for limited and specified use and only following an agreement by the Data Contributors.
- THETIDA will collect data on a need-to-know basis and solely for the purposes of the project.
- All data obtained from THETIDA activities (e.g. online surveys, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, discussions) will be subject to pseudonymization, while personal identifiers (i.e. name, surname, contact details) will be replaced with placeholder values (i.e. participant identification numbers or participant IDs) to safeguard the anonymity of the participants.
- Access to personal information will be monitored and logged while access to data will be restricted using appropriate authentication and authorization techniques (passwords, private keys etc.). Only minimum access privileges required to fulfil their roles will be granted to individuals and systems.
- Data sharing with third parties will be allowed on a case-by-case basis and strictly after approval by the Data Contributor(s).
- Participants will have access to relevant contact information, and they will be informed about the data protection rights and available channels of communication with the THETIDA Project personnel to be able to access, rectify, cancel and oppose the processing and storage of their personal data.
- Personnel of research institutes working with personal data will be aware of their responsibilities and obligations with respect to data protection.

In case of a data breach, the Ethics Manager is responsible to notify authorities and the affected data subjects in the event of a data breach.

3.5.2 Technical safeguards

Technical safeguards focus on guaranteeing the security and protection of electronic information and include the use of the following measures to regulate access, encrypt data, monitor activities, prevent unauthorized changes and ensure safe data transfer procedures during data sharing between project participants:

- Secure computation techniques will be employed to obtain necessary processing results without centralizing all information in a single location.
- Encrypted communication, utilizing SSL/TLS/SSH (Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security / Secure Shell protocol), will be implemented for the transfer of data or information, particularly personal data, between systems and/or project partners. Furthermore, no data will be retained in print.

The Data Controller (ICCS) operates from a secure building, safeguarded internally and externally by a 24-hour security guard (or surveillance). All incoming employees or visitors undergo checks or monitoring.

3.6 Management of potential ethical misconduct

All THETIDA partners are committed to complying with relevant norms and rules for good scientific practice as laid down in national and international codes of conduct as well as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [7]. The EIM with the support of ELC will monitor the compliance of all ethical issues and identify any cases of misconduct (incl. fabrications, falsification, plagiarism) throughout the lifetime of the project. Suspected research misconduct will be reported to and investigated internally by the ELC.

4. Conclusions

The deliverable focused on ethical guidelines for engaging human participants and the protection of personal data in THETIDA project with the main aim to ensure transparency and compliance with ethical standards throughout the processes followed by project activities. An outline of the procedures and criteria to identify and recruit participants for project activities is also provided alongside with detailed information about the procedure to be followed to voluntarily obtain informed consent of participants and specific forms that need to be filled. Finally, it provides templates of informed consent forms, information sheets, and invitation letters to be used for future THETIDA events and activities.

References

- [1] The Ethics Appraisal Scheme in Horizon Europe. Available: https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/The-Ethics-Appraisal-Scheme- BBMRI-webinar-september-2021_version-for-dessimination.pdf [Accessed: 07/03/2024]
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- [6] Deliverable 7.3 (2023). Early project management handbook, and reports on innovation, data and IPR management. THETIDA project, GA number:101095253. pp. 1-77.
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Annex I: Ethical & Legal Review decision template

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

Ethical & Legal review decision template

DX.X – [insert title of Deliverable]	
Dissemination Level: PU / CO	Deliverable Type: R / DEM / OTHER
REVIEWED BY Person name / partner short name	DATE

Ethics and Legal Review Process

Each deliverable that may contain legal, ethical or security issues will be initially reviewed by the EIM and then if required (e.g. grounds exist for ethical/legal concerns) it will be forwarded to two members of the THETIDA ELC that will be assigned for further review. The ELC review will take place in parallel with the quality review performed by THETIDA partners.

This form will be filled in by the EIM and if required by the two ELC members that have been assigned for further review. Each reviewer will upload the completed form to the relevant deliverable folder on THETIDA sharepoint.

Following this review, the EIM and/or ELC members will conclude whether the deliverable is given approval or not by ticking the appropriate box (replacing the box with an 'x'):

- EIM/ELC approval granted** – no changes required
- ELC approval granted** – subject to required changes (see comments below)
- ELC approval pending** – clarification and second round of ELC review required (see comments below)
- ELC approval denied** – see comments below

ELC reviewer’s comments	Author’s responses

Please note:

- All comments and questions raised by the EIM/ELC reviewers should be addressed;
- Approval is not intended to convey any judgement on the quality of the deliverable;
- In case of conflicting or unclear reviews, the author of the deliverable notifies the EIM/ELC by email, whereby the ELC discusses the issue at hand, provides the author with clarification and makes any necessary amendments to the review;
- Any additional legal, ethical or security issues arising during the course of the project must be reported to the EIM/ELC.

Annex II: List of THETIDA deliverables that may contain legal, ethical or security issues

The following deliverables may contain legal, ethical or security issues. They therefore need to be reviewed by the THETIDA Ethics & Legal Committee (ELC) before submission to the EC.

Del. No	Deliverable name	Delivery date
D3.1	THETIDA LL how-to guide	6
D7.2	Data management plan	6
D7.3	Early project management handbook, and reports on innovation, data and IPR management	6
D1.1	THETIDA End User Needs	9
D3.2	THETIDA Training report	9
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Annex III: THETIDA information sheet template

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

1. THETIDA Information Sheet

In the context of the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme for Research and Innovation, the project THETIDA has received funding under Grant Agreement No. 101095253. The vision of THETIDA is to safeguard and protect Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage (CH) from the effects of climate change and natural hazards following a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to CH sites, promoting in parallel policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas.

For more information about the project, please visit the project's website at: <https://THETIDA.eu/>

This particular activity to which you are invited to participate today relates to < _____ >. You will receive detailed instructions and guidance during the activity by the responsible THETIDA partner < _____ >.

Your identity will not be used somehow by the project. You will be also asked to answer some < _____ >. The data collected during this activity will be processed by THETIDA consortium partners in line with the research objectives of the THETIDA project explained to you in the THETIDA Content sheet.

For these purposes the collected data may be shared only with the following organisations of the THETIDA consortium: < _____ >. Contact details of each THETIDA partner are provided in addendum on the back side of this consent form. You will receive a copy of this consent form.

BY SIGNING AND RETURNING THE PRESENT CONSENT FORM, YOU AGREE THAT:

- you have been informed of and understand the purposes of this activity,
- you have been given the opportunity to ask questions,
- your participation in the THETIDA activities is voluntary,
- you understand you can withdraw your participation and consent at any time without prejudice and
- you consent to the collection and processing for the abovementioned purposes, during and after the activity, and of your responses to questionnaires by the THETIDA partners listed below.

Name of volunteer:

Signature:

Place and date:

Annex IV: THETIDA letter of request to participate in an [workshop / interview / pilot] template

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

Template of Letter of Request to participate in a THETIDA [workshop/interview/pilot]

Dear [Name],

I am writing to you on behalf of the THETIDA project which started in May 2023 and is a programme of 42-months duration supported by EU-funding in context of HORIZON EUROPE.

The core ambition of THETIDA is to safeguard and protect Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage (CH) from the effects of climate change and natural hazards following a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to CH sites, promoting in parallel policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas.

I am seeking your participation in one of the [workshop/interview/demonstration] that will run [date, location].

The THETIDA project consortium assures you that any personal data or information you provide will, unless mandatory law prescribes otherwise, be kept strictly confidential and will be securely stored and retained for the lifetime of the project and, unless mandatory law prescribes otherwise, deleted thereafter.

Furthermore, should you agree to participate in this [planned event], and subsequently feel unable or unwilling to continue, you are free to leave without any consequence. That is, your participation is completely voluntary, and you may withdraw from this project activity at any time.

An information sheet, which describes the project in greater detail, has been prepared to help you make a fully informed decision on participation.

Should you agree to participation, after understanding and accepting the conditions, we will provide you with a consent form on the day of the [workshop/interview/demonstration] that will formalize the conditions of your participation. Should you require further information about the specific event or the project more generally, I would be happy to speak with you. Alternatively, should you not be in a position to participate, we would appreciate any assistance you could provide to find an appropriate replacement.

Looking forward to your response.

Warm Regards,

On behalf of THETIDA project consortium

Project Coordinator

[REDACTED]

Annex V: THETIDA Generic informed consent form template

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

Demonstration/Validation Informed Consent Form template

THETIDA is a 42-month long project, that started in May 2023, and is supported by EU-funding in context of HORIZON EUROPE. The core ambition of THETIDA is to safeguard and protect Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage (CH) from the effects of climate change and natural hazards following a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to CH sites, promoting in parallel policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas.

The THETIDA project requires that anyone who participates in the [use case/trial/pilot demonstration] give explicit consent to do so.

Please take the time to read and understand the following, and if you agree with the content sign the consent form overleaf.

I freely and voluntarily consent to participate in the THETIDA project activity that will be conducted at _____.

The THETIDA project assures you that any data or information you provide will, unless mandatory law prescribes otherwise, be kept strictly confidential. In gathering our data, we will only record information that is necessary to address the central purpose of our research. This information will be securely stored and retained, unless mandatory law prescribes otherwise.

Furthermore, your name will not be linked with the research materials, as the researchers are interested in the content in general, and not in any individual's values or choices.

I, the undersigned, confirm that (please tick box as appropriate):

1.	I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the THETIDA Information Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the THETIDA project and my participation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	I voluntarily agree to participate in the testing/demonstration activity of the THETIDA project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	I understand I can withdraw myself and my data from the project at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalised for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The procedures regarding confidentiality have been clearly explained (in this case anonymization of data) to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	If applicable, separate terms of consent for interviews, audio, video or other forms of data collection have been explained and provided to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.	The use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me. I understand that data will either be destroyed or reused at the end of the research.	<input type="checkbox"/>
8.	I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form.	<input type="checkbox"/>
9.	Select only one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would like my name used and understand what I have said or written as part of this study will be used in reports, publications and other research outputs so that anything I have contributed to this project can be recognised. • I do not want my name used in this project. 	<input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/>
10.	I, along with the THETIDA partner, agree to sign and date this informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Participant:

Name of Participant Signature Date

THETIDA _____ :

Name of THETIDA partner Signature Date

Annex VI: Tailored informed consent form for the workshops of WP3

THETIDA
PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

Grant Agreement Number: 101095253

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

The **Informed Consent Form** consists of:

1. Information sheet;
2. General information about data protection
3. Certificate of consent

Information sheet

This section provides general information about the project and the activities involving the participants.

EU-funded project “THETIDA ” (2023-2026) aims to develop innovative and sustainable ways to safeguard coastal and underwater cultural heritage, particularly monuments, historical buildings, archaeological sites and coastal cultural landscapes from climate change effects, natural hazards and environmental pollution, addressing in particular the need for research on wetting phenomena.

Increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather conditions globally have a major impact on cultural heritage that represents tangible (i.e. monuments, historic buildings and sites, cultural landscapes) and intangible (i.e. knowledge, cultural and social practices, oral traditions) assets that are inherited from the past. Sea level rise, ocean acidification, increased storm intensity, temperature rise and coastal erosion threaten to adversely impact the stability, preservation, conservation and security of tangible and intangible underwater and coastal cultural heritage (CH).

The vision of the THETIDA project is the development of a preventive conservation strategy that includes monitoring, risk preparedness and management, for underwater and coastal CH

sites, to identify and ward off additional threats and promote adaptation, reconstruction, and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to climate change and to wield policy tools for economic resilience.

The Workshop aims to bring together and engage relevant stakeholders and community groups that are involved with and affected by both cultural heritage management and climate change and natural hazards-related issues in the demonstration areas, with the main aim to:

- raise awareness and educate these diverse groups about the impacts of climate change and natural hazards on cultural heritage, and to train them to understand and monitor the physical environmental changes as extracted from technological innovation tools.
- identify the socio-cultural, economic and environmental values and impacts of cultural heritage with the local stakeholder and community groups through participatory citizen engagement tools.
- co-create and co-design sustainable protection, risk-preparedness and adaptation strategies that consider socio-cultural values.

Findings from Workshops and other interventions will be used for the refinement of project specifications and consolidation of requirements customised to the end user needs and to provide feedback for the development of citizen engagement technologies.

The organizers and the project itself cannot pledge that the outputs of workshops and other interventions will be included into the final strategic documents.

Type of intervention

The workshop will take place: <date >, <location>

General information about data protection

Voluntary Participation

Your participation at the workshop or other activity is completely voluntary, and you can stop your participation at any time.

Confidentiality

We will not share any information about you outside of the project team. The information that we collect from this project are kept confidential and only the THETIDA team will be able to see it. No personal data will be passed on and any information about you will be stored securely and handled confidentially. Personal Data will be deleted at project conclusion.

Sharing of workshop findings

We will be sharing what we have learnt with the participants, the THETIDA project partners and with a wider public. Concrete participant statements will be anonymised/pseudonymised on request. We might also publish the results in academic outlets in order that other

interested people may learn from our project. Data will only be included in these publications in aggregated and anonymised form.

Audio and video recordings

Audio and video recordings, if taken, will not be available outside the project team, unless for marketing purposes. On these occasions, we will inform you about the recordings in advance and you have the right to withdraw if you do not consent to being recorded.

Contact persons

In case of any questions or requests, you are invited to get in touch with Project Ethics Manager, Dr. Villy Portouli: v.portouli@iccs.gr

Certificate of consent

I have read the aforementioned information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction.

I hereby give consent for my data to be transmitted, processed and documented uniquely for the purpose stated above. I confirm that I have been informed of the nature of THETIDA project and of the activity I will be participating in and that my participation is voluntary. I am aware that I may withdraw my consent and stop my participation at any time.

I, the undersigned, confirm that (please tick box as appropriate):

I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the Information Sheet.	<input type="radio"/>
I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation.	<input type="radio"/>
I voluntarily agree to participate in the project.	<input type="radio"/>
I understand I can withdraw at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalised for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn.	<input type="radio"/>
The procedures regarding confidentiality have been clearly explained (e.g. use of names, emails, pseudonyms, anonymisation of data, etc.) to me.	<input type="radio"/>
Separate terms of consent for interviews, audio, video or other forms of data collection have been explained and provided to me.	<input type="radio"/>
The use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me.	<input type="radio"/>
I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form.	<input type="radio"/>
I, along with the project team member, agree to sign and date this informed consent form	<input type="radio"/>

A copy of this **Informed Consent Form** has been provided to the participant.

Participant:

_____	_____	_____
Name of Participant	Signature	Date

THETIDA :

_____	_____	_____
Name of THETIDA partner	Signature	Date